

DETECTION OF METABOLIC SYNDROME AND OBESITY AMONG CHILDREN AND ADOLESCENTS IN THE POLYCLINIC

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Abstract: Metabolic syndrome and obesity are an urgent problem both in Uzbekistan and around the world. An increase in incidence with this pathology is observed not only in the adult population, but also in adults under 10 years of age and adolescents[2]. Metabolic syndrome (MS) is a complex of metabolic, hormonal and clinical disorders closely associated with type II diabetes mellitus and are risk factors for the development of cardiovascular diseases, which is based on insulin resistance and compensatory hyperinsulinemia [3].

The purpose of our study is to identify the presence of metabolic syndrome and obesity symptoms in children and adolescents under 10 years of age.

Materials and methods of research. During the examination of 107 children and adolescents with obesity, blood glucose, immunoreactive insulin and C-peptide, lipidogram were identified. The examination was accompanied by ultrasound examination of the abdominal organs, electrocardiography, X-ray of the skull (Turkish saddle) or MRI of the pituitary gland, blood pressure monitoring was carried out.

The results of the study. The study revealed a tendency towards the manifestation of obesity mainly in children over 7 years old. The examination revealed changes in carbohydrate metabolism in the form of impaired carbohydrate tolerance and hyperinsulinemia, dyslipidemia, arterial hypertension. Weight in children decreased significantly against the background of proper nutrition, physical activity, intake of intestinal lipase inhibitors, and blood biochemical parameters improved.

Conclusion. Thus, regardless of the degree of obesity, children have signs of metabolic syndrome such as hyperinsulinemia, dyslipidemia and hypertension. Adherence to an adequate diet, physical activity, and the use of intestinal lipase inhibitors collectively show a positive effect in the treatment of obesity and manifestations of metabolic syndrome in children.

Keywords: Children under 10 years old, adolescents, obesity, metabolic syndrome, complications, treatment, prevention.

Relevance. Today, more than a billion people on the planet are overweight. Overweight is one of the fundamental risk factors for the development of many diseases, such as diabetes mellitus, hypertension, coronary heart disease, liver and gallbladder diseases and other pathologies [4, 7]. The conducted studies and the data obtained suggest that up to 10% of children may be clinically obese, as well as a considerable number of overweight adolescents retain it in adulthood [1, 8].

The role of hereditary factors in the development of obesity is currently beyond doubt. The existence of familial forms of obesity has been sufficiently studied, in which the inheritance coefficient reaches 25%,

which indicates a fairly high influence of genetic factors on the development of this disease [1].

It is believed that several periods are critical for the development of obesity [7]. At 1 year of life, excessive feeding of a child leads to adipocyte hyperplasia. With timely and adequate correction of the diet and diet during this period, there is a high probability of a favorable outcome. At the age of 5-7 years, obesity can be recurrent, which is often persistent and implies permanent obesity in adulthood, because during this period, the excess number of adipocytes does not decrease, but a reserve for fat depots is created [5]. The prevailing majority of overweight adolescents retain their body weight into adulthood. This predisposition is largely due to the restructuring of the neuroendocrine system associated with puberty.

The phenomenon of insulin resistance (IR) is one of the most common metabolic disorders in obesity in children. Free fatty acids prevent the binding of insulin by hepatocytes, which causes the development of IR at the hepatic level, a decrease in the absorption of insulin by the liver and the development of systemic hyperinsulinemia [2, 5]. In laboratory diagnostics at the first stage, additional studies include: assessment of the lipid profile, liver functions, glucose testing and determination of the concentration of immunoreactive insulin and C-peptide; determination of leptin concentration (recommended at the onset of obesity in early childhood and in monogenic forms of obesity) [7].

The purpose of our study is to determine the presence of signs of metabolic syndrome in obese children.

Materials and methods of research. During the examination of 107 children and adolescents with obesity, blood glucose, immunoreactive insulin and C-peptide, lipidogram were identified. The examination was accompanied by ultrasound examination of the abdominal organs, electrocardiography, X-ray of the skull (Turkish saddle) or MRI of the pituitary gland, blood pressure monitoring was carried out. All patients were diagnosed with obesity, taking into account standard deviations of body mass index (SDS BMI) according to WHO criteria.

The results of the study. The study revealed a tendency towards the manifestation of obesity mainly in children over 7 years of age. The examination revealed changes in carbohydrate metabolism in the form of impaired carbohydrate tolerance and hyperinsulinemia, dyslipidemia, arterial hypertension. Weight in children decreased significantly against the background of proper nutrition, physical activity, intake of intestinal lipase inhibitors, and blood biochemical parameters improved.

Of all the obese children we examined, the majority were boys -57%. The age of the children ranged from 3 to 10 years. The age group of 3-7 years included 8 children (12%), from 8 to 12 years - 22 children (34%) and, according to our data, adolescents aged 12 to 17 years turned out to be the overwhelming majority - 54%.

According to the study, 68% of children were breastfed from 3-4 months of age.

The manifestation of obesity was not dependent on the age of the child. The examined children with MS were up to 1 year old in 5% of children; from 1 to 3 years old - in 18% of children; from 4 to 7 years old — 28% of children; over 7 years old, 32% suffered from this pathology. All patients were examined for the purpose of early detection of various signs of metabolic syndrome. During the examination, fasting and post-carbohydrate blood glucose levels, lipidogram, immunoreactive insulin (IRI) and C-peptide, levels of thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) and free thyroxine (T4sv.) were determined. Ultrasound examination of abdominal organs, electrocardiography, X-ray of the skull (Turkish saddle) or MRI of the pituitary gland were performed, blood pressure was monitored. Taking into account the classification of obesity depending on SDS BMI, at the time of the examination, children with grade I obesity were identified - 16% (SDS BMI =2.0-2.5). The proportion of grade II and III obesity accounted for 32% and 35% of children, respectively. Morbid type of obesity (SDS BMI $\geq$ 4) was found in 8% of patients. Taking into account Tanner's criteria, no disorders in sexual development were found in the examined children.

Signs of metabolic syndrome in obese children

Complications	The severity of obesity							
	I degree (n=16)		II degree (n=21)		III degree (n=23)		Morbid (n=5)	
	Abs.	%	Abs.	%	Abs.	%	Abs.	%
Violation of carbohydrate tolerance	0	0	2	9,5	3	13,0	3	60,0
Hyperinsulinemia	1	6,2	8	38,1	10	43,5	4	80,0
Dyslipidemia (or hypercholesterolemia)	1	6,2	3	14,3	4	17,4	4	80,0
Arterial hypertension	2	12,5	15	71,4	16	69,6	5	100

In addition, functional disorders of the thyroid gland were excluded in all children. Upon receiving the results of TSH and T4 CV levels, we excluded functional disorders of the thyroid gland.

As can be seen from the presented data, changes in carbohydrate metabolism were observed in children with II, III degrees of obesity and especially in morbid obesity. However, one patient with grade I obesity also had hyperinsulinemia. Hypercholesterolemia and dyslipidemia were observed in patients with varying degrees of obesity. High blood pressure (episodes or a cardiologist-confirmed diagnosis of hypertension) was recorded in children with both morbid obesity (100%) and grade I (12.5%). Children with II and III degrees of obesity suffer from an approximately equal ratio of increased blood pressure (71.4% and 69.6%, respectively). The children we examined did not suffer from concomitant diseases affecting excessive accumulation of adipose tissue.

Conclusion. Thus, children born full-term, with normal weight indicators, mainly from the age of three, without any concomitant pathology affecting excessive accumulation of adipose tissue, with a burdened family history of obesity, diabetes mellitus, and pathology of the cardiovascular system, suffer from obesity. Regardless of the degree of obesity, children have complications in the form of signs of metabolic syndrome such as hyperinsulinemia, dyslipidemia, arterial hypertension. Proper nutrition, physical activity, and intestinal lipase inhibitors in combination have a positive effect in the treatment of obesity and metabolic syndrome in children [7].

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